

FEATURES OF PREPARING STUDENTS FOR PEDAGOGICAL ACTIVITIES

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Social mechanisms for the formation of educational readiness, necessary for effective and high-quality education in global educational institutions, have been introduced into the educational process. UNESCO Policy Document "Reform and Development of Higher Education" (1995) [1; 2]; UN World Declaration "Higher Education in the 21st Century: Approach and Practical Challenges" (1998) [3]; Bologna Declaration (1998), adopted to ensure uniformity in the quality of European higher education; Systematic work is being carried out to introduce the most advanced teaching methods based on modern pedagogical and information and communication technologies that meet international educational standards, to develop the professional sustainability of future teachers in the context of digitalization of education.

Today, as a result of the large-scale reforms carried out in our Republic, the system of improving the quality of education based on the modern requirements of the world, forming the professional stability of future teachers, creating modern educational resources in Pedagogical higher education institutions, and forming the system of professional stability for pedagogical activities Organization on the basis of international qualification requirements and the regulatory basis for improving educational processes based on credit-module technologies were created. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev at a solemn ceremony dedicated to the Day of Teachers and Trainers. We set ourselves the main goal of creating the foundation of the Ushinshi Renaissance. We put the issue of Ushinshi Renaissance in front of us as a strategic task and raise it to the level of a national idea. We consider the division of institutions to be the four integral rings of the Renaissance. Today, it has become an unprovable fact that modern society cannot develop without the education system. Innovations and promising plans in the education system cannot be implemented without social and state contributions. To clarify the content of the selected model, it is first of all necessary to find out what "social understanding" means [4].

Many scientists deal with the problems of preparing students for professional teaching activities and the formation of its sustainability in the higher education system. Issues of forming a student's personality at a university and increasing the social activity of students on the basis of self-government and diagnostics of professional development M.A. Abdullazhonova, O.A. Abdulina, A.A. Studied in research by Akbarov, K.A. Abdurakhmanova, S.V.Safonova. Scientists and teachers Kh. Abdukurimov, N. Azizkhodjaeva, who in their scientific works explored the professional skills of a teacher, the pedagogical skills of a teacher, the possibilities of using modern innovative educational tech-

nologies of a teacher, as well as the worldview of teachers. future teachers, communicative dialogue. The ways and methods of further development of culture are explored. An analysis of the literature shows that the content and definitions of competence and the competency-based approach, as well as the professional qualities of a modern teacher, have been widely studied.

In the processes of forming the professional stability of future teachers, as one of the ways to increase it, it is necessary to pay attention to the psycho-emotional mental state of students and develop the ability to manage themselves in its implementation. When developing professional stability of students, it is necessary to manage the psycho-emotional state, determine psychological and pedagogical conditions and improve their regulation in the environment of higher education [5].

Psychological stability is a complex personal characteristic that includes "balance, proportion, resilience, stability, tenacity." According to Krupnik and N. Lebedeva, such features are interpreted as a state of dynamic equilibrium, which is ensured by the counteraction of external and labor factors that disrupt the balance. The problem of developing professional stability of future teachers is relevant from the point of view of professional training, and special psychological and pedagogical conditions and means can play an important role in this. These conditions include:

1. Psychophysiological characteristics and psycho-emotional state of students make it possible to predict and prevent undesirable events.

2. Training students in order to increase their psychological and professional competence in the field of self-government in the formation of professional sustainability of future teachers. The higher the level of professional competence, the higher the opportunity for students to choose their psycho-emotional state and methods of self-control in stressful situations.

3. When a pedagogical problem arises, it is necessary to prepare students for professional activities by using special socio-psychological training aimed at developing general professional stability in psycho-emotional situations, which will help students achieve success in future professional activities. It is necessary to take into account the typological characteristics of future teachers when developing students' professional stability, adaptation to the profession and rational organization of work. Thus, many scientific works are devoted to the issues of professional training, in which successful approaches to training are implemented depending on the specific features of professional activity.

A.K. Guz emphasizes that stability is based on an unstable balance between opposing trends - basic and systemic. The first tendency is to remain constant

(tense) and therefore move; the second reflects the desire for change, development, new quality (impermanence).

According to the scientist, stability and instability, stability and imbalance should not be opposed. Resilience exists as a combination of different types and levels of sustainability, system formation trends and system changes. A stable system balances stability, on the one hand, and change and instability, on the other.

The Republic of Uzbekistan requires the implementation of the “National Personnel Training Program” and the development of science and technology, a new approach to the process of training and education, the development of more active forms, methods and teaching techniques. It must be said that the memory method, i.e. the method of “memorizing material”, which is used in teaching, still dominates in our higher educational institutions. American scientists have found that “memorizing facts” and “recalling” in education can reduce the characteristics of a person’s creative growth and cause mental retardation [6].

The memory method - the acquisition of knowledge - is based on memorizing material. Studying abroad is based on the method of thinking, i.e. logical assimilation (understanding) of the material. In addition, it is important to instill a methodological culture of studying abroad, create a methodological culture and cultivate it.

Each lesson is part of the educational process and a logical step in acquiring knowledge, skills and abilities.

Each lesson must meet the following requirements:

1. Clarity of purpose and content. This requirement is fulfilled by taking a short journey into our spirituality and enlightenment and selecting the teaching material and its content for the lesson.

2. Interdependence and integrity of my tasks related to upbringing and education. The educational description of education is determined on the basis of the objective laws of society or the rules of traditional education. In this case, the student must make full use of all opportunities for the formation of professional knowledge.

3. The ability to choose the most necessary teaching methods at any stage of the lesson. The student’s correct choice of teaching method ensures, firstly, the effectiveness of the teacher’s work and, secondly, the highest activity of the student. This forms in students a deep and comprehensive knowledge base and the ability to apply acquired knowledge in practice [7].

4. Carrying out the main work and individual educational work in the lesson to the satisfaction of students. In addition to working with the whole group during the lesson, the teacher should give students individual tasks and involve them in independent work. This could form the basis for future learning. This requirement is met; after reading the theory, a short task will be given to strengthen it.

5. Effective lesson organization. This requirement is the effective use of the time allocated for the lesson, good preparation of the teacher and students for the les-

son, provision of training with constantly updated technical equipment and visual aids, careful planning of all elements and content of the lesson.

The forms, types and brief contents of education are analyzed above. Below, the content, features and content of forms and types of education are analyzed.

Biological science lessons can be two academic hours, and practical laboratory classes can be four or six hours. It is advisable to take a break of at least 5-10 minutes between classes.

When theoretical courses on biology are taught through lectures and the necessary (scheduled) laboratory and practical work is carried out depending on the focus of the goal, four types of classes can be clearly identified:

Type 1 – lesson for learning and teaching new material;

Type 2 – lesson of repetition, consolidation and generalization of knowledge;

Type 3rd – lesson to test knowledge, skills and abilities;

Type 4 - mixed lesson.

The quality of speech and tone of voice of each teacher is different. By practicing tuning, the voice can become pleasant. It is necessary to eliminate certain speech defects, for example, speaking out of breath, “swallowing” the last part of a word, and similar defects. It is necessary to clear speech of parasitic words.

It is very helpful for the student to find a tone of voice in which he/she feels comfortable speaking. This transition from tone to tone enlivens speech.

Low tone is important. The teacher’s voice is considered normal and can be heard even by the students sitting in the last row filling the auditorium [8]. However, a voice that is too loud can make reading boring. It is necessary to change the speed and level of speech, as well as tone, depending on the level of complexity and importance of the educational material. Important laws and regulations are best presented louder and slower than simpler or unimportant material. Always try to speak clearly and clearly. New terms should be especially clear.

Experienced teachers, in the process of explaining educational material, take a short pause between some sentences and after each important idea or tariff. This moment increases students’ attention and gives them time to understand the material being presented.

Speech technique is the result of a student’s daily work. For its continuous improvement, the following is recommended: monitor how others speak, analyze the advantages and disadvantages of the speech of your colleagues, as well as those who spoke at meetings, lectures, conferences;

always try to practice your speech;

the best way to make speech highly cultural and technical is to speak in front of a large audience at meetings, councils, seminars, and teaching classes.

Briefly, in the process of professional and methodological training of students from biology to teaching; knowledge and practical application of innovative educational technologies; be able to deeply understand interdisciplinary connections when teaching not only

biology, but also other sciences; be able to fully understand and apply the methodology of biology and natural sciences; they must have a stable education in psychological and pedagogical terms, have good laboratory and practical training, and have the skills to work with students and involve them in topics.

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